

Supplementary Materials

Pelagic zone is an evolutionary catalyst, but an ecological dead end, for North American minnows

Figure S1. Rate of phenotypic evolution across evenly-spaced groups based on mouth angle (i.e., each group contains the same range of mouth angles but uneven numbers of species). Contrast with Figure 4 in the main text using four quartiles (i.e., each group contains even numbers of species but uneven ranges of mouth angles).